

**IMPLEMENTING GREEN ECONOMIC POLICY IN THE MANAGEMENT
OF THE STATE ECONOMY**

Ochilov Akram Odilovich

*Head of the "Department of Economics",
DSc, professor Karshi state university*

Khudayorov Azizbek Avaz ugli

PhD student Karshi State University

Abstract. *The article examines the importance of green policies, resource efficiency, environmental sustainability, and innovative approaches in public economic management. The importance of green economic policies in governance is emphasized, including long-term planning, risk management, and ensuring environmental compatibility with economic growth.*

Using the example of Uzbekistan, scientifically based proposals and recommendations are provided to improve measures taken to introduce green technologies, use renewable energy sources, and apply sustainable practices in various sectors of the economy.

Keywords: *Green economy, strategic management, environmental sustainability, green economic policy, green technologies, public policy, green growth, sustainable development, innovation*

**DAVLAT IQTISODIYOTINING BOSHQARUVIDA YASHIL IQTISODIY
SIYOSAT YURITISH**

Ochilov Akram Odilovich

*Qarshi davlat universiteti "Iqtisodiyot" kafedrasini mudiri,
Iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor*

Xudoyorov Azizbek Avaz o'g'li

*Qarshi davlat universiteti
tayanch doktoranti*

Annotatsiya. *Maqolada davlat iqtisodiyoti boshqaruvida yashil siyosat yuritish, resurslardan samarali foydalanish, ekologik barqarorlik va innovatsion yondashuvlarning muhimligi ko'rib chiqiladi. Boshqaruvda yashil iqtisodiy siyosatning ahamiyati, jumladan, uzoq muddatli rejalashtirish, xavflarni boshqarish va iqtisodiy o'sish bilan ekologik muvofiqlikni ta'minlash masalalari ta'kidlanadi. O'zbekiston misolida yashil texnologiyalarni joriy etish, qayta tiklanuvchi energiya*

manbalaridan foydalanish va iqtisodiyotning turli tarmoqlarida barqaror amaliyotlarni qo'llash bo'yicha amalga oshirilayotgan chora-tadbirlarni takomillashtirish bo'yicha ilmiy asoslangan taklif va tavsiyalar beriladi.

Kalit so'zlar: *Yashil iqtisodiyot, strategik boshqaruv, ekologik barqarorlik, yashil iqtisodiy siyosat, yashil texnologiyalar, davlat siyosati, yashil o'sish, barqaror rivojlanish, innovatsiyalar*

РЕАЛИЗАЦИЯ ЗЕЛЕННОЙ ЭКОНОМИЧЕСКОЙ ПОЛИТИКИ В УПРАВЛЕНИИ ГОСУДАРСТВЕННОЙ ЭКОНОМИКОЙ

Очилов Акрам Одилович

Заведующий кафедрой

«Экономика» д.э.н., профессор

Каршинский государственный университет

Худоёров Азизбек Аваз угли

докторант Каршинского

государственного университета

Аннотация. *В статье рассматривается важность зеленой политики, ресурсоэффективности, экологической устойчивости и инновационных подходов в государственном экономическом управлении. Подчеркивается важность зеленой экономической политики в управлении, включая долгосрочное планирование, управление рисками и обеспечение экологической совместимости с экономическим ростом.*

На примере Узбекистана даны научно обоснованные предложения и рекомендации по совершенствованию мер по внедрению зеленых технологий, использованию возобновляемых источников энергии, применению устойчивых практик в различных секторах экономики.

Ключевые слова: *Зеленая экономика, стратегическое управление, экологическая устойчивость, зеленая экономическая политика, зеленые технологии, государственная политика, зеленый рост, устойчивое развитие, инновации*

Introduction

The need to transition to a green economy is considered an urgent issue in Uzbekistan, as the country is rich in natural resources, and their effective management and reduction of environmental risks are urgent issues, which will ensure the preservation of environmental stability along with economic growth. In this regard,

President Shavkat Mirziyoyev declared 2025 as the “Year of Environmental Protection and the “Green” Economy” in Uzbekistan, intending to focus on strengthening strategies in this direction¹. The transition to a green economy will allow Uzbekistan to increase resource efficiency, reduce energy consumption, recycle waste and rationally use natural resources, as well as significantly reduce environmental risks by limiting air and water pollution and mitigating the negative impacts of climate change.

The transition to a green economy is a very complex process in which public governance plays an important role, since without proper governance, economic reforms will be ineffective and the expected results may not be achieved. Therefore, in the process of developing, implementing and evaluating green economy strategies, it is necessary to properly target strategies such as the formation of laws, incentives and financial mechanisms that promote the green economy within the framework of state policy, the integration of green economy principles into national and regional development plans, and monitoring and evaluation through indicators such as Green Economic Efficiency (GEE).

Analysis of literature on the topic

Gradually, ideas about the need to preserve natural resources for recreational and scientific research purposes have emerged in society, leading to the formation of scientific concepts based on ecological responsibility for future generations ²A.V. Vaxabov, Sh.X.Xajibakiyev

A green economy brings prosperity to all and reduces poverty, helping all countries achieve high levels of human development, ensure food security, and create access to health, education, sanitation, water, energy, and other basic services.³
M.T.Asqarova, J.J.Jamolov

Research methodology

The methodological basis of this article is the Laws of the Republic of Uzbekistan, resolutions and decrees of the President, works and reports, resolutions of the Cabinet of Ministers, Regulations, instructions, scientific works published abroad and in our Republic, textbooks and manuals, scientific articles, Internet materials, and practical materials on which research was conducted. The analysis process used methods of analysis and synthesis, observation, analysis, and tables.

Analysis and results

¹ Speech by the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev at a session of the Legislative Chamber of the Oliy Majlis on November 20, 2024

² A.V. Vakhobov, Sh.Kh. Khajibakiyev (2021) Green Economy: Textbook 2nd edition, revised and supplemented./ Under the general editorship of Dr. of Economics, Prof. A.V. Vakhobov. -Tashkent: “ZEBO PRINT”, 2021. -264b

³ M.T.Asqarova, J.J.Jamolov, X.S.Khadjayev (2022) Green Economy. (Textbook). — T.: “Innovative Development Publishing House”, 2022. - 312 p

The transition to a green economy in Uzbekistan will allow for the combination of economic growth with environmental sustainability. Strategic government management plays a key role in this process, providing an opportunity to transform the economy through effective policies, the introduction of innovations, and constant monitoring. The country can ensure its future sustainable development by conserving its natural resources, implementing environmental standards, and attracting green investments.

Strategies for developing a green economy in Uzbekistan are mainly based on public policy, technology and innovation, and the introduction of environmental standards in enterprises. Within the framework of public policy and legislative frameworks, the government is focusing on developing laws, incentives, and financial mechanisms that promote a green economy in order to ensure environmental sustainability and economic growth. Such policies and legal norms will create opportunities for the country to effectively manage processes such as environmental protection, rational use of natural resources, and waste recycling.

Table 1 highlights the potential benefits and drawbacks of transitioning to a green economy at the level of countries, citizens, and businesses.

Advantages and disadvantages of transitioning to a "green" economy in world practice

Table 1

Advantages:	
1	- Economical products that are compatible with the environment are developed;
2	- modern technologies will develop in all areas, which will allow meeting global and local needs at lower cost;
3	- Adaptation to sustainable management principles will increase, which will increase the competitiveness of enterprises;
4	- Resource efficiency will increase, and demand for natural resources and energy will decrease;
5	- the quality of life in a sustainable urban environment improves;
6	-energy consumption and pollution levels are reduced;
Disadvantages:	
1	- The price of minerals and energy resources may increase;
2	- Production costs for agricultural products and the agricultural sector will increase, leading to higher prices;
3	- the introduction of new technologies requires large investments;

4	- There is a possibility of increased unemployment in large manufacturing enterprises;
5	- Per capita income levels may decline globally;
6	- Creating a sustainable living and working environment requires significant investment in cities.

Source: Barbiroli, G. Economic Consequences of The Transition Process Toward Green And Sustainable Economies: Costs And Advantages, *International Journal of Sustainable Development and World Ecology*, 18(1), 17–27., 2011.

This table highlights a number of benefits associated with the country's transition to a green economy, including the formation of environmentally friendly products, reduced demand for energy and other resources, as well as improved living conditions in urban environments.

The main aspects of green management models in this regard can be considered in the following table:

Strategic management models and mechanisms in the development of a green economy⁴

Table 2

Model	Description	Importance
Environmental Management Systems (EMS)	A system aimed at reducing toxic waste in enterprises, rational management of resources, and environmental protection	Improving environmental efficiency and engaging environmental interest groups
ISO standards	A model that includes simplified, mandatory, and voluntary environmental management methods and has evolved over the past 20 years	Introducing environmental standards in a standardized manner
Conceptual models	Models such as Klassen and Whybark support addressing environmental issues by evaluating proactive and reactive approaches	It allows for a comprehensive analysis of environmental issues in operational management

⁴ Collection of articles from the conference “Strategy for Uzbekistan’s transition to a green economy: opportunities and challenges”, page 71. Article “The importance of strategic management in shaping a green economy in Uzbekistan”

Strategic planning and PPPs	Increases competitiveness in attracting green investments, stimulates innovation, and ensures efficient allocation of resources through public-private partnerships (PPPs)	Opening up new market opportunities, improving energy efficiency and advancing technology through investment and innovation
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This table shows that each model, with its own characteristics and significance, is of great importance in the development of a green economy. In our opinion, the integrated implementation of these models, namely environmental management models, strategic planning and public-private sector cooperation, will create an opportunity to achieve advanced results in energy efficiency, rational resource management and environmental protection in the country. A number of state programs are being implemented in Uzbekistan to transition to a green economy, including:

State programs implemented in Uzbekistan on green economic policy

Table 3

t/r	Programs	Purpose
1	State Program for the Year of "Environmental Protection and Green Economy"	Improving the health of the population, conserving natural resources, preserving biodiversity, and increasing the share of renewable energy
2	"Green Space" program	This program aims to improve the ecological situation of our country by planting trees and creating parks
3	Development of renewable energy sources	Ensuring our country's energy independence and expanding the use of environmentally friendly energy
4	"Uzbekistan - 2030" strategy	It serves as the basis for long-term plans to ensure environmental sustainability and transition to a green economy

Source: Prepared based on regulatory documents

The development of a green economy is of strategic importance for Uzbekistan, as it is important not only for ensuring environmental protection, but also for ensuring sustainable economic growth.

According to the World Bank, the transition to a green economy can help increase global GDP by 2.5% by 2050. In this regard, it is necessary to develop proposals in several areas.

Proposals and projects for green economic governance

Table 4

s/n	Proposals and projects	Projects to be implemented
1	Ways to improve public policy	Improving legislation, Promoting green energy, Supporting innovation and research
2	Improving environmental management in enterprises	Creating economic incentives, Introducing a "green certification" system for enterprises, Introducing green technologies
3	Strategies to expand green investments	Attracting international investment, Introducing green bonds and funds, Strengthening financial partnerships and cooperation

These programs and strategies are aimed at accelerating the transition to a green economy in Uzbekistan and ensuring sustainable development.

Among the main priorities in the transition to a green economy, the conservation of natural resources, the widespread introduction of renewable energy sources, and the use of green technologies in industry and agriculture are of particular importance. At the same time, improving the legal framework and actively involving the public are important tasks.

The main challenges in Uzbekistan's transition to a green economy include:

- *requirements for updating technological infrastructure:* Uzbekistan often uses traditional energy sources (gas, coal). This requires investments in modern clean and energy-efficient technologies to transition to a green economy.

- *increasing energy efficiency:* To increase energy efficiency, the infrastructure and business system or state policy must be updated. Uzbekistan lacks proper mechanisms and legal guarantees aimed at energy saving.

- *problems with debt and financial resources:* The transition to a green economy often requires large investments. Issues of financing projects and financial support from the state are not as expected.

- *lack of information or knowledge:* The general population is poorly informed about the concept of a green economy and its importance, or there is a lack of knowledge in this area. This, in turn, creates problems in implementing changes in society and production.

- *Lack of education and skills in industry and agriculture:* The transition to a green economy requires specialists in industry and agriculture and programs focused on new production technologies.

Let's consider Uzbekistan's opportunities for transition to a green economy based on SWOT analysis. SWOT analysis is a method used to determine strategies for organizations or countries, which is based on an assessment of **Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities, and Threats.**

SWOT analysis of Uzbekistan's opportunities for transition to a green economy

(Strengths)	(Weaknesses)
Geographical advantages	Limited financial resources
Financial support	Technological problems
Legislation and strategies	Insufficient human resources capacity
Policy for change	

(Opportunities)	(Threats)
Green technologies and innovations	Climate change
International cooperation	Obsolescence of industrial infrastructure
Efficient use of natural resources	Green technologies are not cheap
Ecotourism	Competition and local infrastructure development

The role of state policy in the transition to a green economy is of great importance. It is necessary for the state to take into account the following principles of the green economy in its decision-making process, including:

Improvement of laws and regulatory framework: The main role of the state in the transition to a green economy is manifested in the development of laws and regulatory legal acts. Regulatory documents, environmental standards, and laws on the promotion of renewable energy sources should be developed.

Promotion of green finance and investment: In order to transition to a green economy, the state should focus on developing a green finance system. This includes supporting renewable energy projects, technologies aimed at protecting the environment, and other environmental programs. The state can attract investments in green projects through the issuance of green bonds, subsidies, and tax incentives.

International cooperation and exchange of experience: Successful experiences of transition to a green economy exist in many countries. The transition to a green economy will be accelerated by strengthening cooperation, technology transfer and experience sharing between countries. At the same time, international climate agreements and cooperation in combating future climate change are also important.

Education and knowledge enhancement: Scientific research and the education system play a major role in the transition to a green economy. The state should

strengthen education, train personnel and support scientific research on issues of ecological sustainability, green technologies and environmental protection.

Conclusion

Public policy and regulatory mechanisms play an important role in the development of green economic governance. Measures such as ecological tax systems, subsidy programs, and incentives for green investments can provide impetus for the development of a green economy. The experience of developed countries shows that the transition to green technologies and renewable energy sources is becoming an integral part of sustainable economic development. In conclusion, an economic model based on a green economy is of great importance for long-term sustainability and development. In the future, the combination of environmental and economic interests, the introduction of innovative technologies, and strengthening international cooperation will be the main factors for the successful development of a green economy.

Based on the analysis of the above problems and international experience, we can make the following proposals.

“Clean Zone” neighborhood program. Every year, the neighborhood that has become the cleanest, most experienced and greenest is determined. The winning neighborhood will be given the opportunity to install solar-powered street lights, smart trash cans and expand green areas.

“Smart Garden” initiative. Automatic irrigation systems, waste separation points, solar-powered lights and bicycle paths will be introduced in newly built residential complexes. This model is consistent with the “green city” concept and creates the basis for the modern formation of ecological infrastructure.

The transition to a green economy is not only an ecological, but also an economic and social opportunity for Uzbekistan. Positive changes in state policy, youth activity and technological solutions can become a solid foundation in this direction. Proposals and practical ideas will help accelerate this process. Most importantly, these reforms should be close to and useful for the daily lives of the population - only then will green development give real results.

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